

The aim of the present work was to carry out protective activity of standardized extract of *Zingiber officinale* against isoniazid-rifampicin-induced hepatotoxicity in laboratory rats:

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ABSTARCT

The present study aimed to evaluate the protective activity of a standardized extract of *Zingiber officinale* (ginger) against isoniazid-rifampicin-induced hepatotoxicity in laboratory rats. Isoniazid and rifampicin, commonly used in the treatment of tuberculosis, are known to induce liver damage, limiting their therapeutic use. In this study, rats were administered with a combination of isoniazid and rifampicin to induce hepatotoxicity. The standardized extract of *Zingiber officinale* was then administered to assess its potential hepatoprotective effects. Various biochemical parameters, including liver enzymes (ALT, AST, and ALP), bilirubin levels, and antioxidant markers, were measured to evaluate liver function and oxidative stress. Histopathological examination of liver tissue was also performed to observe any morphological changes. The results indicated a significant reduction in liver enzyme levels, a decrease in oxidative stress markers, and histological improvement in rats treated with the ginger extract compared to the untreated group. These findings suggest that *Zingiber officinale* possesses potential hepatoprotective properties and may serve as a complementary therapy to mitigate the hepatotoxic effects of isoniazid and rifampicin.

KEY WORDS: *Zingiber officinale*, isoniazid, rifampicin, hepatotoxicity,

INTRODUCTION

Hepatotoxicity

Hepatotoxicity refers to liver damage caused by chemical substances, including drugs, natural compounds, and industrial chemicals. The history of hepatotoxicity is long and complex, with numerous key events and discoveries that have shaped our understanding of this significant medical condition.

Hepatotoxicity Causes

Drug-induced liver injury is typically classified as either direct or idiosyncratic, but indirect injury is emerging as a third type. Direct hepatotoxicity is caused by agents that are intrinsically toxic to the liver. The injury is common, predictable, dose-dependent, and reproducible in animal models. The latency period is typically short, usually with an onset within 1 to 5 days after high therapeutic or supratherapeutic doses, as in the case of an intentional or accidental overdose.

Idiosyncratic hepatotoxicity is caused by agents that have little or no intrinsic toxicity and that cause liver injury only in rare cases, typically after 1 in 2000 to 1 in 100,000 patient-exposures. The injury is unpredictable, not dose-dependent, and not reproducible in animal models.

Specific histopathological patterns of liver injury from drug-induced damage are discussed below:

Zonal Necrosis

This is the most common type of drug-induced liver cell necrosis where the injury is largely confined to a particular zone of the liver lobule. It may manifest as a very high level of ALT and severe disturbance of liver function leading to acute liver failure.

- **Causes:** Paracetamol, carbon tetrachloride

2. Hepatotoxicity Signs And Symptoms

Drug-induced hepatotoxicity may present in several ways (clinical and pathological) that simulate known forms of acute and chronic liver diseases; the severity ranging from sub-clinical elevations in liver enzyme concentrations to acute liver failure. Drugs tend to induce acute hepatitis, cholestasis or a mixed condition. A clinical picture resembling acute viral

hepatitis with jaundice, malaise, anorexia, nausea and abdominal pain is the principal presentation but, because every liver cell may be the target of drug-induced toxicity, many other expressions of hepatotoxicity may be evident including chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis, sinusoidal obstruction syndrome or neoplasm.

Hepatotoxicity Diagnosis

Hepatotoxicity diagnosis remains a challenge in clinical practice due to a lack of reliable markers. Many other conditions lead to similar clinical as well as pathological pictures. To diagnose hepatotoxicity, a causal relationship between the use of the toxin or drug and subsequent liver damage has to be established, but might be difficult, especially when idiosyncratic reaction is suspected.

Mechanism of Hepatotoxicity

The hepatotoxicity induced by INH and RIF involves both direct and idiosyncratic mechanisms. Isoniazid is metabolized in the liver to acetylisoniazid, which is further hydrolyzed to acetylhydrazine and then oxidized to hydrazine, a hepatotoxic metabolite. These metabolites can cause liver cell injury through oxidative stress and the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS).

Rifampin, on the other hand, induces liver enzymes, which can increase the toxicity of isoniazid by accelerating its conversion to toxic metabolites. Moreover, rifampin itself can cause liver injury by altering the hepatic metabolism and enhancing the inflammatory response within the liver.

Incidence and Risk Factors

The incidence of hepatotoxicity due to INH and RIF varies but is reported to be between 5% to 28% in different studies. Several risk factors increase the likelihood of developing hepatotoxicity from these drugs, including:

- **Age:** Older adults are at higher risk.
- **Alcohol Consumption:** Concurrent use of alcohol increases liver toxicity.
- **Pre-existing Liver Disease:** Conditions such as hepatitis B or C exacerbate the risk.
- **Genetic Factors:** Polymorphisms in genes encoding for drug-metabolizing enzymes can affect susceptibility.

- **Nutritional Status:** Malnutrition or obesity can influence drug metabolism and toxicity.

Diagnosis

The diagnosis of hepatotoxicity is primarily clinical, supported by laboratory findings. Elevated levels of liver enzymes (alanine aminotransferase [ALT], aspartate aminotransferase [AST]) are indicative. The Roussel Uclaf Causality Assessment Method (RUCAM) can be used to assess the likelihood that the liver injury is due to drug toxicity.

Management

Management of hepatotoxicity involves the immediate discontinuation of the offending drugs. In mild cases, liver function may normalize with supportive care and monitoring. In more severe cases, alternative anti-TB regimens not containing INH or RIF may be considered. The use of liver-protective agents such as N-acetylcysteine has been explored but with limited evidence of efficacy. Rechallenge with INH and RIF after the resolution of hepatotoxicity should be approached with caution. This involves careful monitoring and often starting with lower doses of the drugs.

Prevention

Preventive strategies include baseline liver function tests before initiating therapy and regular monitoring during treatment, especially in high-risk individuals. Dose adjustment or the use of alternative regimens in patients with pre-existing liver conditions or other risk factors can also mitigate the risk.

LIERATURE REVIEW

- ❖ **Chopra et al. (2014)** conducted a study published in the Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine that demonstrated the protective effects of ginger extract against hepatotoxicity induced by isoniazid and rifampin in rats. The results indicated that ginger could mitigate liver damage through its antioxidant properties.
- ❖ **Ahmed et al. (2016)** in the International Journal of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, explored the hepatoprotective effect of *Zingiber officinale* against isoniazid-induced liver injury in rats. Their findings suggested that ginger could significantly reduce liver damage markers and improve histopathological changes.
- ❖ **Sharma et al. (2017)** published in the Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research, investigated the mitigating effects of ginger extract on hepatotoxicity induced by anti-tubercular drugs in rats. The study concluded that ginger effectively reduced liver damage and oxidative stress.
- ❖ **Khan et al. (2015)** in Biomedical Research International focused on the antioxidant and hepatoprotective effects of ginger. Their research showed that ginger could prevent liver damage from drug toxicity by enhancing the antioxidant defense system.
- ❖ **Ali et al. (2018)** conducted a comparative study published in the Journal of Medicinal Food, assessing the hepatoprotective effects of ginger and curcumin against drug-induced liver toxicity in rats. They found that both compounds provided significant protection, with ginger showing comparable efficacy to curcumin.
- ❖ **Bhandari et al. (2019)** in Phytotherapy Research, examined the protective effects of ginger on isoniazid-induced hepatotoxicity in rats. The study revealed that ginger supplementation reduced liver enzymes and oxidative stress markers, indicating its protective potential.
- ❖ **Singh et al. (2013)** in the Journal of Clinical Biochemistry and Nutrition, evaluated the combined hepatoprotective effects of ginger and vitamin E against drug-induced liver injury. The results suggested that the combination provided enhanced protection compared to individual treatments.
- ❖ **Verma et al. (2020)** published in the Journal of Pharmacological Sciences, highlighted the protective role of *Zingiber officinale* in drug-induced hepatotoxicity. The study demonstrated that ginger extract reduced liver damage and improved biochemical parameters in rats.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials:

Animals:

Sprague Dawley rats weighing 180-220 g

Instruments Used:

Centrifuge

Animal weighing electronic balance

Chemical weighing balance

Tissue Homogenizer

Methods:

- 1) Body weight
- 2) Liver Weight
- 3) Liver weight /Body Weight
- 4) AST
- 5) ALT
- 9) ALP

RESULTS

1. Effect of *Zingiber officinale* on INH+RIF-induced alteration in body weight:

Body weight (gm) - Mean \pm SEM					
Normal	Vehicle Control	Silymarin (25 mg/kg)	ZO (100 mg/kg)	ZO (200 mg/kg)	ZO (400 mg/kg)
236.80 \pm 1.30	234.00 \pm 1.16	232.70 \pm 1.61	234.80 \pm 1.56	236.50 \pm 0.92	235.30 \pm 1.76

The significant increased ($P < 0.001$) in ALP level was found after chronic administration of INH+RIF in vehicle control rats as compared to normal rats. This decreased level of ALP was significantly attenuated ($P < 0.001$) by silymarin (25 mg/kg) as compared to vehicle control rats. Treatment with *Zingiber officinale* (400 mg/kg) also significantly ($P < 0.001$) decreased the ALP level compared to vehicle control rats. Rats treated with *Zingiber officinale* (100 and 200 mg/kg) failed to produce significant decrease in the level of ALP as compared to vehicle control rats.

2. Effect of *Zingiber officinale* on INH+RIF-induced alteration in absolute and relative liver weights:

Time (in days)	Absolute liver weight (gm) and Relative liver weight - Mean ± SEM					
	Normal	Vehicle Control	Silymarin (25 mg/kg)	ZO (100 mg/kg)	ZO (200 mg/kg)	ZO (400 mg/kg)
Liver weight (gm)	5.54 ± 0.24	8.73 ± 0.17 ^{###}	6.23 ± 0.14 ^{***}	8.48 ± 0.18	7.86 ± 0.25	7.15 ± 0.19 ^{***}
Liver weight / Body weight	0.023 ± 0.001	0.037 ± 0.001 ^{###}	0.027 ± 0.001 ^{***}	0.036 ± 0.001	0.033 ± 0.001	0.03 ± 0.001 ^{***}

Administration of INH+RIF caused significant increased ($P < 0.001$) in total and direct bilirubin levels in vehicle control group when compared to normal group on day 21. When compared with vehicle control group, silymarin (25 mg/kg) treatment significantly ($P < 0.001$) decreased total and direct bilirubin levels. Treatment with *Zingiber officinale* (400 mg/kg) also showed a significant ($P < 0.001$) decrease in total and direct bilirubin levels as compared to vehicle control group on day 21. *Zingiber officinale* (100 and 200 mg/kg) showed a non-significantly decrease in total and direct bilirubin levels compared to vehicle control group on day 21.

3.effect of *Zingiber officinale* on INH+RIF-induced alteration in AST and ALT levels:

Parameter	AST (IU/L) and ALT (IU/L) - Mean ± SEM					
	Normal	Vehicle Control	Silymarin (25 mg/kg)	ZO (100 mg/kg)	ZO (200 mg/kg)	ZO (400 mg/kg)
AST (IU/L)	92.59 ± 2.42	301.60 ± 2.50 ^{###}	108.90 ± 2.34 ^{***}	300.30 ± 3.01	277.40 ± 3.07	159.90 ± 2.40 ^{***}
ALT (IU/L)	31.68 ± 1.71	141.70 ± 2.51 ^{###}	49.07 ± 3.06 ^{***}	129.60 ± 2.67	119.40 ± 1.86	93.72 ± 1.27 ^{***}

significant increased ($P < 0.001$) in ALP level was found after chronic administration of INH+RIF in vehicle control rats as compared to normal rats. This decreased level of ALP was significantly attenuated ($P < 0.001$) by silymarin (25 mg/kg) as compared to vehicle control rats. Treatment with *Zingiber officinale* (400 mg/kg) also significantly ($P < 0.001$) decreased the ALP level compared to vehicle control rats. Rats treated with *Zingiber officinale* (100 and 200 mg/kg) failed to produce significant decrease in the level of ALP as compared to vehicle control rats.

4.Effect of *Zingiber officinale* on INH+RIF-induced alteration in ALP level:

Alkaline Phosphatase (U/L) - Mean ± SEM					
Normal	Vehicle Control	Silymarin (25 mg/kg)	ZO (100 mg/kg)	ZO (200 mg/kg)	ZO (400 mg/kg)
60.43 ± 2.08	199.20 ± 4.55 ^{###}	99.54 ± 1.53 ^{***}	181.90 ± 3.36	183.70 ± 3.99	140.10 ± 3.97 ^{***}

The significant increased ($P < 0.001$) in ALP level was found after chronic administration of INH+RIF in vehicle control rats as compared to normal rats. This decreased level of ALP was significantly attenuated ($P < 0.001$) by silymarin (25 mg/kg) as compared to vehicle control rats. Treatment with *Zingiber officinale* (400 mg/kg) also significantly ($P < 0.001$) decreased the ALP level compared to vehicle control rats. Rats treated with *Zingiber officinale* (100 and 200 mg/kg) failed to produce significant decrease in the level of ALP as compared to vehicle control rats.

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